

SUSTAINABLE POLYMER MATERIALS: EFFECT OF AGRICULTURAL WASTE REINFORCEMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF PBS AND PBAT COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The increasing accumulation of post-consumer plastic waste, particularly from single-use packaging, has intensified global concerns regarding environmental sustainability. Currently, plastic packaging constitutes nearly half of all plastic waste generated worldwide, highlighting the urgent need for sustainable alternatives. In response, the plastics industry is undergoing a transition from petroleum-based polymers to biodegradable, compostable, and biobased materials. However, the adoption of biodegradable polymers remains limited by their lower mechanical strength, durability, and processing performance compared to conventional plastics. To address these limitations, the use of green composites represents a promising solution, offering not only materials with enhanced performance but also cost-effective. This study explores the use of natural fillers to improve the properties of biodegradable polymers such as polybutylene succinate (PBS) and polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT). Agricultural by-products such as rice straw and wheat straw were used as reinforcement at loadings up to 30 wt.%. Mechanical (tensile, flexural) tests and thermal (TGA, DSC) analyses were conducted on both neat polymers and composite formulations to evaluate performance improvements. Results show that incorporating 30 wt.% wheat straw significantly promoted the mechanical properties of both polymers. For PBS-based composites, tensile strength increased by approximately 16.5%, with >400% rise in tensile modulus. PBAT-based composites demonstrated even greater enhancements, including a 42.9% increase in tensile strength and a significant improvement in Young's modulus compared to pure PBAT.

1 INTRODUCTION

The extensive use of petroleum-based polymers, such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC), has resulted in their accumulation in the environment. These materials are adopted in different sectors from packaging and automotive components to medical devices and construction. However, their environmental persistence has emerged as one of the most pressing challenges of our century [1]. Due to their chemical inertness, high hydrophobicity, and mechanical durability, these polymers resist degradation in natural environments, leading to their long-term accumulation in terrestrial and marine ecosystems. This buildup, often termed "white pollution," results not only in visual alteration but also in profound ecological consequences, including harm to wildlife, soil fertility degradation, and microplastic contamination of food chains [2].

To address this environmental issue, researchers and industries have turned to biodegradable polymers as more sustainable alternatives. Biodegradable plastics such as poly(lactic acid) (PLA), polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) like polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate (PHBV), poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT), and poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) offer the potential to reduce long-term environmental impact by breaking down into non-toxic by-products (CO_2 and H_2O) under biodegradation or composting conditions. These materials, derived from renewable or partially renewable sources, have gained attention not only for their ecological compatibility but also for their potential to support circular economy models and reduce dependence on fossil resources [3].

PBS and PBAT are examples of biodegradable aliphatic polyesters: PBS is synthesized through the polycondensation of succinic acid and 1,4-butanediol and is known for its high thermal resistance, good ductility and compatibility with conventional polymer processing techniques, including injection molding and extrusion [4]. These properties make PBS a suitable candidate for various applications, especially in food packaging, mulching films, and disposable items. PBAT, an aliphatic-aromatic copolyester composed of 1,4-butanediol, adipic acid, and terephthalic acid, possesses high ductility and impact resistance. It is often used in films, bags, and packaging applications that require high elongation at break. However, PBAT is derived from fossil-fuel sources and suffers from relatively low mechanical strength, which can limit its adoption [5].

Despite the intrinsic ecological benefits of PBS and PBAT, their widespread commercial adoption faces several obstacles. These include the relatively high production costs and low durability [6].

To address these shortcomings, in particular performance and cost, one promising strategy is the incorporation of fillers into biodegradable polymer matrices to enhance tensile strength, thermal stability, stiffness, and impact resistance. Natural fillers derived from renewable agricultural by-products represent an interesting solution due to their low cost, availability, renewability, and intrinsic biodegradability. Among these there are lignocellulosic residues, such as straw, husks and plant fibers. These materials are rich in cellulose and lignin, making them suitable for reinforcement purposes when properly processed and introduced into polymer matrices [7]. These wastes are often discarded, underutilized, or burned contributing to environmental degradation and greenhouse gas emissions. Their addition into biodegradable polymers not only provides an effective waste management strategy but also adds value to agricultural by-products by transforming them into functional eco-friendly materials. This dual benefit aligns with global sustainability goals and supports rural economies [8]. In this context, wheat and rice straws represent examples of lignocellulosic agricultural residues that can serve as reinforcing materials: their potential has been mainly explored in polylactic acid (PLA)-based composites, especially when used as fibers. Results in literature have demonstrated that the addition of these fibers can significantly enhance the tensile and flexural properties of PLA matrix when fibers are adequately processed. Common strategies to improve fiber-matrix adhesion include chemical modifications such as alkaline treatment, silane modification, and grafting with compatibilizers. These treatments alter the fiber surface by removing impurities, increasing surface roughness, and introducing reactive functional groups that promote interfacial bonding with the polymer matrix.

Feng et al. [9] demonstrated that the addition of 30 wt.% of NaOH and silane-treated rice straw fibers into a PLA/PBAT blend enhanced its mechanical properties, resulting in a tensile strength of 12 MPa and a flexural strength of 18 MPa. Similarly, Beniwal et al. [10] used PLA-grafted rice straw fibers to improve dispersion and adhesion within PLA matrix, leading to enhanced mechanical performance and biodegradability. In the case of wheat straw, Liao et al. [2] introduced the 30 wt.% of fibers treated with alkaline and hydrogen peroxide into PLA and observed improved tensile strength and modulus. They also explored the effects of adding PBS to the formulation. Berthet et al. [11] investigated the role of fiber size and surface characteristics by adding wheat straw fibers into PHBV matrix, observing changes in thermal stability and mechanical behavior depending on fiber content and processing conditions.

The biodegradability attitude of the polymer is maintained in the presence of such natural fillers. Pradhan et al. [12] observed that PLA filled with 30 wt.% of wheat straw maintains its compostable nature. Furthermore, these bio-based fillers can impart tunable properties to composites, such as improved water vapor permeability due to their inherent hydrophilicity [11] and contribute to economic sustainability with potential cost reductions of up to 30%.

While most of the works previously summarized focused on PLA-based systems and waste fibers, this study examines the effect of as-received wheat and rice straw incorporated into PBS and PBAT

matrices, without specific particle size selection or chemical modification, to assess their intrinsic reinforcement capabilities, aiming for more environmentally and economically sustainable manufacturing operations. The mechanical properties of the materials were evaluated under quasi-static conditions through tensile and flexural tests. In addition, the thermal characteristics of the composites were analyzed by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), while morphological analysis by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was useful to point out the interfacial features that influence composite performance.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Rice straw (RS) was provided by Azienda Riso Milano (Italy) and wheat straw (WS) by Agriturismo Cascina Scanna (Italy). Both straws were washed with tap water and oven-dried at 80 °C for 24 hours. As a final step, the materials were ground using a knife mill and sieved through a 1 mm mesh sieve.

PBS and PBAT maleic anhydride (MA) grafted granules were purchased from Auser Polimeri (Italy). The polymers have a density equal to 1.26 g/cm³ (ISO 1183) and melt mass flow rate of 8 g/10 min and 4 g/10 min, respectively (measured at 190 °C and 2.16 kg, ISO 1133). The MA content is ≤0.1%.

The composite materials were prepared using a two-stage process involving extrusion (co-rotating twin-screw extruder, Thermo Scientific Process 11, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and injection molding (Haake MiniJet IPro, Thermo Fisher Scientific). During melt compounding, the following temperature profile from feeder to die was adopted: 145 °C—155 °C—155 °C—160 °C—170 °C—170 °C—165 °C—165 °C. The screw speed was set at 150 rpm. During the injection, a pressure of 450 bar was maintained for 10 s and a post-injection was operated at 150 bar for 10 s. The mold was maintained at 50 °C while the loading cylinder was kept at 165 °C. Prior to extrusion, the pellets and fillers were dried at 80 °C overnight.

The particle size distribution (PSD) of WS and RS was analyzed using a Microtrac Sync laser diffraction particle size analyzer (Verder Scientific S.r.l., Bergamo, Italy). Measurements were conducted in dry mode, applying a dispersion pressure of 100 kPa and a suction pressure of 70 kPa. The PSD of the fillers is reported as percentile values: D10, D50, and D90. D10 represents the particle diameter below which 10% of the sample (by mass or volume) is finer; D50 corresponds to the median particle size, where 50% of the sample is finer; and D90 denotes the diameter below which 90% of the particles are finer.

Tensile and flexural properties of both neat polymers and composite samples were evaluated using a Zwick/Roell Z010 universal testing machine. Tensile tests were performed under displacement control at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min and ambient temperature, following the ISO 527-2 standard (specimen type 1BA, gauge length $l_0 = 30$ mm). Three-point bending tests were conducted in accordance with ISO 178, using specimens with dimensions of 80 × 10 × 4 mm, a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min, and a span-to-thickness ratio of 16:1. Each test was carried out with a minimum of five replications.

Thermogravimetric (TGA) analysis was carried out according to ISO 11358 by heating the samples (around 20 mg) from room temperature to 800 °C under nitrogen atmosphere (50 mL/min) and with a heating rate of 10 °C/min (TG209 F1 Libra instrument by Netzsch). Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was performed according to ISO 11357 with a nitrogen flow of 60 mL/min (DSC 214 Polyma by Netzsch). Specimens (around 10 mg) were analyzed with a temperature program from -100 °C to 200 °C with a heating/cooling/heating rate of 10 °C/min. Results for melting and crystallization temperatures, as well as the degree of crystallinity (X_c , Equation 1), are reported as the mean values of three repetitions:

$$X_c (\%) = \Delta H_m / [\Delta H_m^0 \cdot w_c] \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where the subscript "c" specifies the polymer (PBS or PBAT), ΔH_m is its measured enthalpy of melting in J/g, ΔH_m^0 the enthalpy of melting of fully crystalline polymer equal to 110.3 J/g for PBS [13] and 114.0 J/g for PBAT [14]. w is the polymer mass fraction in the composite.

3 RESULTS

From a thermal perspective, the addition of both fillers into the polymer matrices, in agreement with

findings reported in the literature [15,16], affects the thermal stability of the final composites. This is primarily attributed to the degradation of the hemicellulose components present in the straw-based fillers, which typically decompose at lower temperatures compared to the degradation temperatures of the neat polymer matrices. TGA data supports this observation: the onset of thermal degradation, defined as the temperature at which 5% weight loss occurs ($T_{5\%}$), decreased by 17.0% and 20.0% for PBS matrix composites reinforced with WS and RS, respectively. While for PBAT matrix composites, both fillers induced a comparable reduction of approximately 27.0%. Such values are calculated with respect to the $T_{5\%}$ of the neat polymers, observed at 341.1 °C for PBS and 362.2 °C for PBAT.

From DSC analyses no significant variations in the characteristic thermal transition temperatures such as glass transition, melting and crystallization were observed with the addition of both fillers. However, differences were in the degree of crystallinity of the polymer matrices (calculated according to Equation 1). Neat PBS exhibited a superior degree of crystallinity (61.5%) compared to PBAT (10.0%) while, in presence of WS and RS, the crystallinity of PBS decreased by 14.7% and 2.0% with WS and RS, respectively. For PBAT, the reduction was 5.4% and 4.4% for WS and RS, respectively. These findings indicate that no nucleating effect occurs for either type of filler [17].

Formulations	Tensile strength [MPa]	Flexural strength [MPa]	Young's Modulus [GPa]	Flexural Modulus [GPa]
<i>PBS</i>	33.8 (± 1.0)	44.1 (± 1.4)	0.7 (± 0.1)	0.9 (± 0.1)
<i>PBS_30WS</i>	40.5 (± 1.5)	64.3 (± 1.2)	3.7 (± 0.6)	2.9 (± 0.2)
<i>PBS_30RS</i>	38.1 (± 1.3)	60.3 (± 2.3)	2.7 (± 0.4)	1.9 (± 0.3)
<i>PBAT</i>	11.0 (± 3.6)	5.8 (± 0.2)	0.1 (± 0.1)	0.1 (± 0.1)
<i>PBAT_30WS</i>	15.7 (± 0.3)	27.2 (± 1.0)	1.0 (± 0.1)	1.0 (± 0.2)
<i>PBAT_30RS</i>	14.5 (± 0.4)	24.1 (± 0.6)	0.9 (± 0.2)	0.7 (± 0.1)

Table 1: Quasi-static mechanical properties of polymers and composites.

Table 1 summarizes the results of mechanical characterization, including strength and modulus values under both tensile and flexural loading conditions. Although the materials investigated are grafted polymer formulations, the overall mechanical performances of the neat polymers are consistent with values reported in the literature for both PBS [18] and PBAT [19], also in agreement with their degrees of crystallinity [20], as previously discussed in the DSC results.

The introduction of rigid lignocellulosic fillers led to a significant increase in stiffness, both in tension and in bending. This behavior is typical of composites reinforced with natural fillers [21,22] and, as comparison, the enhancement observed with the addition of 30 wt.% of WS was greater than that recorded for composites with 30 wt.% of RS, in both polymer matrices.

Percentile values	WS Size [μm]	RS Size [μm]
<i>D10</i>	29.4	69.6
<i>D50</i>	181.5	286.8
<i>D90</i>	256.4	464.7

Table 2: Particle size distribution of WS and RS.

This difference can reasonably be attributed to heterogeneities in particle morphology (shape and size) between the two fillers. This is demonstrated by SEM micrographs (Figure 1a–b), where it is possible to notice in both fillers a high morphological heterogeneity, and from results in Table 2 where are summarized the particle size distributions by their cumulative percentiles. WS exhibits a finer

dimension compared to RS, which likely facilitates better distribution of the filler into the matrix and promotes a better load transmission at the interface due to a larger surface area. This interpretation is supported by findings from Berthet et al. [12], who reported that stiffness enhancements are more pronounced when the specific surface area of the filler increases, even in the presence of limited interfacial adhesion. Although the fracture surface micrographs (Figure 1c–f) display signs of fiber pull-out and visible gaps between the matrix and the filler, typically associated with limited interfacial adhesion between the hydrophobic polymer matrices and the hydrophilic lignocellulosic reinforcements [23,24], the overall interfacial bonding is not significantly compromised (Figure 1c), owing to the MA-grafted nature of both polymers.

Figure 1: SEM micrographs of (a) WS and (b) RS fillers, and fracture surfaces of composites: (c) PBS_30WS, (d) PBS_30RS, (e) PBAT_30WS and (f) PBAT_30RS.

Interestingly, for both types of fillers, the tensile and flexural strengths also increased, albeit to a lesser extent than the moduli. This trend is consistent with observations by Kumar et al. [16] who measured a superior tensile strength in PBS with 30 wt.% of untreated sisal fibers composites than the neat polymer of about 15.8%. In general, a possible explanation for this behavior lies in the combined effect of chemical anchoring (promoted by the presence of MA) and mechanical interlocking effect, wherein the surface roughness of the lignocellulosic particles acts as anchoring points within the matrix,

thereby improving load transfer at the interface [25]. The enhancements observed in tensile and flexural strengths were superior in the PBAT based formulations compared to those with PBS matrix and this is because of the higher ductility of PBAT than PBS (with the highest deformation at maximum tensile strength of $86.1\% \pm 5.2\%$ compared to $16.6\% \pm 1.5\%$), which allows for a more effective mechanical interlocking.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the thermal and mechanical behavior of biodegradable polymer composites based on PBS and PBAT matrices reinforced with lignocellulosic by-products, specifically wheat straw (WS) and rice straw (RS). TGA results demonstrated a reduction in the onset degradation temperature upon filler addition, primarily due to the early decomposition of hemicellulose components present in both straws. DSC analysis revealed no significant changes in the characteristic thermal transitions; however, a reduction in crystallinity was observed for both matrices, with PBS showing a more substantial decrease. This suggests the absence of a nucleating effect. The addition of straw fillers significantly improved the stiffness of both polymers under tensile and flexural conditions, with WS proving more effective than RS. This enhancement is attributed to the finer morphology and higher surface area of WS, which facilitates more efficient stress transfer. Despite the limited interfacial adhesion between the hydrophilic fillers and the hydrophobic matrices, the mechanical interlocking effect contributed to strength improvements, particularly in the PBAT based composites.

Overall, the results confirm the potential of such agricultural by-products such as cost-effective and sustainable reinforcing agents in biodegradable polymer systems. However, further optimization, especially at the interface level, is essential to fully exploit their reinforcing capabilities.

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